

Comparison of the Linux and Windows Device Driver Architectures

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the device driver architectures currently used by two of the most popular operating systems, Linux and Microsoft's Windows, are examined. Driver components required when implementing device drivers for each operating system are presented and compared. The process of implementing a driver, for each operating system, that performs I/O to a kernel buffer is also presented. The paper concludes by examining the device driver development environments and facilities provided to developers by each operating system

Keywords: Kernel, Linux, Operating Systems, Windows

Introduction

Modern operating system kernels consist of a number of components such as a memory manager, process scheduler, hardware abstraction layer (HAL) and security manager. For a detailed look at the Windows kernel refer to [Rusinovich, 98] and for the Linux kernel [Rusling, 99], [Beck et al, 98]. The kernel can be viewed as a black box that should know how to interact with the many different types of hardware devices that exist and the many more devices that do not yet exist. Creating a kernel that has inbuilt functionality for interacting with all known hardware devices may be possible but is not practical. It would consume too many system resources, needlessly.

Device Driver Architectures

A device driver enables the operation of a piece of hardware by exposing a programming interface that allows a device to be controlled externally by applications and parts of an operating system. This section presents the driver architectures currently in use by two of the most commonly used operating systems, Microsoft's Windows and Linux, and the origin of their architecture.

1. The Windows Driver Architecture

There are two types of Windows drivers, legacy and Plug and Play (PnP) drivers. The focus here is only on PnP drivers, as all drivers should be PnP drivers where the possible. PnP drivers are user friendly since very little effort is required from users to install them. Another benefit of making drivers PnP is that they get loaded by the operating system only when needed, thus they do not use up system resources needlessly. Legacy drivers were implemented for Microsoft's earlier operating systems and their

architecture is outdated. The Windows Driver Model (WDM) is a standard model specified by Microsoft [Microsoft DDK, 02]. WDM drivers are usable on all of Microsoft's recent operating systems (Windows 95 and later).

2. The Linux Driver Architecture

Drivers in Linux are represented as modules, which are pieces of code that extend the functionality of the Linux kernel [Rubini et al, 01]. Modules can be layered as shown in figure 1. Communication between modules is achieved using function calls. At load time a module exports all functions it wants to make public to a symbol table that the Linux kernel maintains. These functions are then visible to all modules. Access to devices is done through a hardware abstraction layer (HAL) whose implementation depends on the hardware platform that the kernel is compiled for, e.g. x86 or SPARC.

Figure 1 The Linux Driver Architecture

Windows Drivers Components

Drivers in Windows consist of various routines. Some are required, others optional. This section presents the routines that every driver must implement. A device driver in Windows is represented by a structure called a DriverObject. It is necessary to represent a driver with a structure such as a driver object because the kernel implements various routines that can be performed for every driver. These routines, discussed in the following sections, operate on a driver object.

1. Driver Initialisation

Every device driver in Windows contains a routine called DriverEntry. As its name suggests, this routine is the first driver routine executed when a driver is loaded and is where initialisation of the device driver's device object is performed. Microsoft's DDK [Microsoft DDK, 02] states that a driver object represents a currently loaded kernel driver whereas a device object represents a physical, logical or virtual device. A single loaded kernel driver (represented by a driver object) can manage multiple devices (represented by device objects). During initialisation, fields in the device object that specify the driver's unload routine, add device routine and dispatch routines are set. The unload routine is a routine that is called when the driver is about to be unloaded so that it can perform cleanup operations e.g. freeing up memory allocated off the kernel heap. addDevice is a routine that is called after the DriverEntry routine if the driver being loaded is a PnP driver, while the dispatch routines are routines that implement driver I/O operations.

2. The AddDevice Routine

PnP drivers implement a routine called AddDevice. In this routine a device object is created at, which time space for storing global data for a device is allocated. Device resource allocation and initialisation is also performed. Device objects are referred to by different names depending on where they where created. If a device object is created in a currently loaded driver to manage that driver, it is called a Function Device Object (FDO). If it is a device object from a lower driver in a stack of drivers, it is called a Physical Device Object (PDO). If it is a device object from an upper driver in a stack of drivers, it is called a Filter Driver Object (FIDO).

I. Creating a device object

A device object corresponding to a device is created using the I/O Manager routine called IoCreateDevice

inside the add device routine. The most important requirements for IoCreateDevice are a name for the device object and device type. The name allows applications and other kernel drivers to gain a handle to the driver, in order to perform I/O operations. The device type specifies the type of device the driver is used for, for example a storage device.

II. Global Driver Data

When a device object is created it is possible to associate with it a block of memory, called DeviceExtension in Windows, where custom driver data can be stored. This is an important facility, as it eliminates the need to use global data structures in driver code, which can be difficult to manage. For example, in the case where a local variable with the same name as a global variable is declared in a routine mistakenly, the driver writer may find it difficult to track a bug in the driver. It also makes it easier to manage device object specific data, when more than one device object exists in a single driver, as is the case when a bus driver manages child physical device objects for devices present on its bus.

III. Device naming

A device can be named at device object creation time. This name can be used for accessing a handle to a driver. The handle is then used for performing I/O. Microsoft recommends not naming functional device objects created in filter and functional drivers. As pointed out by Oney [Oney, 99], if a device object is named, any client can open the device object and perform I/O for non-disk device drivers. This is because the default access control status Windows gives to non-disk device objects is an unrestricted one. Another problem is that the name specified does not have to follow any naming protocol, so the name specified may not be a well chosen one. For example two driver writers may come up with the same name for their device objects, which would cause a clash.

Windows supports a second device object naming scheme using device interfaces. Device interfaces are constructed with 128 bit globally unique identifiers (GUIDs) [Open Group, 97]. A GUID can be generated using a utility provided by the Microsoft DDK. Once generated, a GUID can be publicised. A driver registers the GUID for a device interface in its add device routine through a call to the I/O manager routine IoRegisterDeviceInterface. Once registered, the driver must enable the device interface through a call to the I/O manager routine IoSetDeviceInterfaceState. The registration process

will add an interface data entry to the Windows registry file, which can be accessed by applications.

3. Dispatch Routines

Dispatch routines are routines that handle incoming I/O requests packaged as IRPs (I/O request packets). When an IRP arrives (e.g. when an application initiates I/O), an appropriate dispatch routine is selected from the array of routines specified in the MajorFunction field of a driver object as shown in figure 2. These dispatch routines are initialised in the driver's entry routine. Every IRP is associated with an I/O stack location structure (used for storing an IRP's parameters) when created. This structure contains a field, which specifies the dispatch routine the IRP is meant for and the relevant parameters for that dispatch routine. The I/O manager determines from an IRP which dispatch routine it will send IRPs to.

Figure 2 dispatching IRP's to dispatch routines.

Thus IRPs are routed to an appropriate driver supplied routine so that they can be handled there. Required dispatch routine IDs are shown in table 1. They are indexes for the array of routines specified by the MajorFunction field of a device object. The dispatch routines have custom driver supplied names that are implemented by the driver. They all accept an IRP and a device object to which the IRP is being sent.

IRP_MJ_PNP	Handles PnP messages
IRP_MJ_CREATE	Handles the opening of device to gain a handle
IRP_MJ_CLEANUP	Handles the closing of the device handle gained above
IRP_MJ_CLOSE	Same as clean up, called after cleanup
IRP_MJ_READ	Handles a read request to a device
IRP_MJ_WRITE	Handles a write request to a device

IRP_MJ_DEVICE_CONTROL Handles a I/O control request to a device

IRP_MJ_SYSTEM_CONTROL Handles WMI requests

IRP_MJ_POWER Handles power management messages

Table 1 Required Windows driver dispatch routines

4. Windows Driver Installation

Windows uses installation information contained in a text file called an INF file to install drivers. The creator of a driver is responsible for providing an INF file for the driver. A GUI application that is provided with the Windows DDK called GenInf allows the generation of an INF file for a driver. It requires a company name and a Windows Device class under which the driver will be installed. Windows has various pre-defined device classes for installed drivers. The Windows device manager applet, accessible through the system control panel applet, shows all installed drivers categorised using these device classes. Examples of existing classes are the 1394 and PCMCIA device classes. A custom device class can be added by adding a ClassInstall32 section in the INF file.

The hardware ID for a PnP-aware device must also be specified in the INF file since it will be used by the system to identify the device when the device is inserted into the system. A hardware ID is an identification string used by the PnP manager to identify devices that are inserted into the system. Microsoft publishes PnP hardware IDs for the various devices that are usable with the Windows operating system. This hardware ID is stored on the hardware device and read off the device by the system when that device is inserted into the system. Once an INF file for a new device is successfully installed into the system, the driver for that device (which has a specific hardware ID) will be loaded each time the device is inserted into the system and unloaded when the device is removed from the system.

Linux Driver Architecture Components

Device drivers in Linux are similar to those in Windows in that they too are made up of various routines that perform I/O and device control operations. There is no driver object visible to a

driver, instead drivers are internally managed by the kernel.

1. Driver Initialisation

Every driver in Linux contains a register driver routine and a deregister driver routine. The register driver routine is the counterpart to the Windows driver entry routine. Driver writers use the `module_init` and `module_exit` kernel defined macros to specify custom routines that will be designated as the register and deregister routines.

a. Driver Registration and Deregistration

The routine designated by the `module_init` macro as the registration routine is the first routine executed when a driver is loaded. The driver is registered here by using a kernel character device registration routine called `register_chrdev`. The important requirements for this routine are a name for the driver, a driver major number (discussed later in section 3.2.2) and a set of routines for performing file operations. Other driver-specific initialisation should take place in this routine. The deregistration routine gets executed when the driver is being unloaded. Its function is to perform cleanup operations before a driver is unloaded. A call to the kernel routine `unregister_chrdev` with a device name and major number is necessary when deregistering a driver that was previously registered with a `register_chrdev` call.

2. Device Naming

In Linux, devices are named using numbers in the range 0 to 255, called device major numbers. This implies that there can be a maximum of 256 usable devices i.e. devices that an application can gain a handle to, but each driver for such a major device can manage as many as 256 additional devices. These driver-managed devices are numbered using numbers in the range 0 to 255, called device minor numbers. It is therefore possible for applications to gain access up to 65535 (256x256) devices. Major numbers are assigned to well known devices for example major number 171 is assigned to IEEE1394 devices. The file `Documentation/devices.txt` in the Linux kernel source tree contains all major number assignments and a contact address for the device number registration authority. Currently, major numbers 240-254 are available for experimental use. A driver can specify a major number of 0 to request automatic assignment of a major number for a device, if one is available. The use of major number 0 for this purpose does not cause problems, as it is reserved for the null device and no new driver should register itself as a the null device driver.

a. Driver Access from an Application

Drivers are accessed by applications through file system entries (nodes). By convention, the drivers directory is `/dev` on a particular system. Applications that want to perform I/O with a driver use the open system call to obtain a handle to a particular driver. The open system call requires a device node name such as `/dev/tty` and access flags. After obtaining a handle, the application can use the handle in calls to other system I/O calls such as `read`, `write` and `IOCTL`.

3. Linux Driver Installation

Drivers are installed in Linux by transferring the driver files into a system specific directory. In the RedHat distribution [Redhat, 02], modules are located in the directory `/lib/modules/kernel_version` where `kernel_version` specifies the version of the kernel currently loaded e.g. 2.4.19. A configuration file called `modules.conf` located in the system's configuration file directory e.g. `/etc`, is used by the kernel while loading modules. It can be used to override the location for a particular driver. It is also used for defining other module loading options, such as defining parameters to be passed to a driver when loading it.

Module loading and unloading is performed using programs that come with the kernel module utilities package called `insmod`, `modprobe` and `rmmod`. `Insmod` and `modprobe` load the binary image of a driver into the kernel and `rmmod` removes it. Another program called `lsmod` lists all currently loaded modules. `Insmod` will attempt to load a module and return an error if the module being loaded depends on other modules. `modprobe` will try to satisfy module dependencies by attempting to load any modules the current module may depend on before loading it. The module dependency information is obtained from a file called `modules.dep` located in the system's modules directory.

Before a driver can be accessible to applications, a device node (see sections 2.1 and 3.2.2.1 for how Linux represents devices in the system) for that driver, with the devices major and minor numbers, must be created in the devices directory `/dev`. A system program called `mknod` is used for this purpose. When creating a device node, it is necessary to specify whether the node is for a character device or a block device.

The Windows And Linux Driver Architecture Components Compared

Drivers in both Windows and Linux are dynamically loadable modules that consist of various routines that perform I/O. When loading a module, the kernel will locate a the routine designated by the particular operating system as the driver entry routine and It will start driver code execution from there.

1) Driver Routines

Drivers in both systems have initialisation and de-initialisation routines. In Linux, both these routines can have custom names. In Windows, the initialisation routine name is fixed (called DriverEntry) but the de-initialisation routine can be a custom one. Windows manages a driver object structure for each loaded driver. Multiple instances of a driver are each represented by a device object. In Linux, the Kernel maintains information for each driver registered to manage a device major number. i.e. for each driver that acts as a major device driver.

Both operating systems require drivers to implement standard I/O routines, which are called dispatch routines in Windows and file operations in Linux. In Linux, a different set of file operations can be provided for each device handle returned to an application. In Windows, dispatch routines are defined once in the DriverEntry routine inside a driver object. Since there is one driver object for each loaded driver, it is not advisable to modify the dispatch routines assigned to it when an application requests a handle through an open call. Windows drivers have an add device routine that gets called by the PnP manager for PnP aware devices. There is no PnP manager in Linux and such a routine does not exist in Linux.

Dispatch routines in Windows operate on device objects and IRPs. In Linux, file operations operate on a file structure. Custom global driver data is stored in device objects in Windows and in the file structure in Linux. A device object is created at load time in Windows whereas in Linux a file structure is created when an application requests a handle to a driver with a system open call. An important implication of this is that in Linux global data per application can be kept in the file operations structure. In Windows, global data can only be present in the FDO that the driver manages. Global data per application in Windows has to be kept in a list structure contained within the FDO's custom data structure.

2) Device Naming

Drivers in Windows are named using driver-defined strings and are found in the \\device namespace. In Linux, drivers are given textual names but applications are not required to know these. Driver identification is performed through the use of a major-minor number pair. Major and minor numbers are in the range 0-255, since a 16 bit number is used to represent the major-minor pair thus allowing a maximum of 65535 devices to be installed in a system.

Devices in Linux are accessible to applications through file system nodes. In most Linux distributions the directory /dev contains device file system nodes. Each node is created with a driver's major and minor number. Applications obtain a handle to a driver, for performing I/O, through the open system call targeted at a device file system node. In Windows, another driver naming method exists, whereby a 128 bit GUID is registered by each driver. Applications access the Windows registry to obtain a textual name in the \\device namespace using the GUID. This textual name is used to obtain a handle for performing I/O with a driver through the CreateFile Win32 API call.

3) Driver Installation and Management

Driver installation is through a text file called an INF file in Windows. Once installed, the driver for a device will be automatically loaded by the PnP manager when the device is present in the system. In a Linux system, programs are used to load driver binary images into the kernel. Entries need to be inserted manually into system start up files, so that driver loading programs like modprobe are executed with a driver image path or an alias to the driver as a parameter. Driver aliases are defined in the file /etc/modules.conf, which programs like modprobe inspect before loading a driver. An example of an alias entry in modules.conf would be "alias sounddriver testdriver", which aliases the name sounddriver to the driver binary image testdriver. Executing modprobe with sounddriver as a parameter would make modprobe load testdriver. In this way, users can use a standard and simpler name such as sounddriver to load a sound driver without having to know what the name of a specific driver for a sound card is. Driver status information is available in Windows through the device manager applet, or directly reading the data from the system registry. In Linux, driver information is available through entries in the proc file system. The file /proc/module for example contains a list of loaded modules.

Related Works

The Windows device driver architecture is documented by documentation that accompanies the Windows Device Driver Development kit [Microsoft DDK, 02]. Further, the works produced by Walter Oney [Oney, 99] and Chris Cant [Cant, 99] present a detailed account of the Windows Driver Architecture. The Linux device driver architecture is documented well by the freely available publication authored by Rubini et al [Rubini et al, 01].

Conclusion

This study strongly suggests that IT professionals who are considering deployment of the workloads evaluated should consider far more than the acquisition costs of the technologies that they are investigating. Other factors, such as strategic IT choices, company standards, IT staff skills and competencies, application availability, application deployment, and performance considerations, should be considered as part of a total platform evaluation. IT professionals who are considering the broader strategic deployment of Linux within their IT environments, in particular, should carefully consider these findings and examine all aspects of the cost associated with Linux server systems. Many drivers of cost need to be uncovered in such an examination and evaluation, and the "risk/return" trade-offs of Linux versus Windows may not be as obvious as they appear at first glance.

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